
Phytochemical Analysis and Antimicrobial Potential of *Terminalia arjuna* (Roxb) Wt. & Arn.

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Abstract *Terminalia arjuna* (Roxb) Wt. & Arn) was screened for ethanol (EtOH), n-hexane (n-Hex), ethyl acetate (EtOAc), chloroform (CHCl₃) and aqueous (AQ) fractions for the determination of phytochemical constituents and antimicrobial activity. Results of phytochemical analysis showed that *T. arjuna* have significant phenolic, flavonoids and antioxidant activity. Highest total phenolics (112.6 mg GAE 100g⁻¹) and flavonoids moiety (75.0 mg QE 100g⁻¹) was observed in EtOH extracts whereas notable antioxidant activity (81.2%) was recorded in EtOAc fraction. The *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity were determined by disc and well diffusion method. Promising bactericidal and fungicidal activity was recorded for EtOH (72.41%) and AQ (63.15%) fractions against *Bacillus* sp and *Trichoderma* sp with MIC value of 2.5 mg ml⁻¹ and 10 mg ml⁻¹. It was also observed that EtOH extract exhibits broad spectrum activity by inhibiting all the bacterial strains. However, all the test fungal strains were resistible to n-Hex fraction. From the study, it was suggested that antimicrobial and antioxidant potential of the subject plant extracts might be due to the presence of phenols and flavonoids moiety.

Keywords *Terminalia arjuna*; Antioxidant Activity, Antibacterial Activity, Antifungal Activity

Introduction

Resistibility to existing antimicrobial drugs has coerced the pharmacist to discern and isolate new antibacterial agents of plant origin to treat serious chronic ailments [1]. Exploitation of natural drugs instead of antibiotic is the modern concern due to increasingly multidrug resistance phenomenon [2]. Microbial isolates are one of the leading causes of infectious diseases worldwide [3]. Literature survey divulge that plants are novel source of bioactive compounds such as peptides, unsaturated fatty acids, alkaloids, phenols, aldehydes, essential oils and other soluble moiety that exhibits significant role to eradicate drastic pathogens such as viruses, bacteria and fungi [4]. Plant based drugs are more advantageous in modern medication system because they are biodegradable, safe and have fewer side effects than synthetic ones [5].

Terminalia arjuna (Roxb) Wt. and Arn. (Combretaceae) is a large evergreen tree distributed throughout India, Chota, Nagpur, Orissa, West Bengal, Himalayan tract, Deccan and Konkan [6-7]. The leaf is simple and smooth while the bark is thick. The plant bears regular small, cup shaped and polygamous sessile flower having white to greenish white color during the month of April-July. Inflorescences are small terminal panicles or a short axillary spike. The shape of fruits are oblong and the color may varies from dark reddish brown to reddish brown ripening from February to May [8]. They are used in traditional medication system for the treatments of angina, expectorant, antidiarrhetic, purgative, laxative, leucoderma, anaemia, hyperhidrosis, asthma, tumors cardiovascular disorders [9-10]. It also possesses good anticancer, antiviral and antimicrobial activities [11]. The plant synthesizes numerous bioactive compounds such as tannins, terpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids and polyphenols which are mainly responsible for antimicrobial activities [12-14].

Materials and Methods

Collection of Plants

The fruits of exotic wild plant *T. arjuna* was collected from the vicinity of Swat valley at their matured stage. The sample was thoroughly washed with tap water followed by distilled water. All the impurities such as dust, dirt and debris was removed and kept in shade for complete dryness. The sample was crushed with electrical grinder (Yigan, model WF130) and stored in clean plastic bags with proper labelling.

Extraction and Fractionation

About 1.5 Kg of powder sample was soaked in 2.0 L ethanol for several days. Ethanol solution was filtered and concentrated on rotary evaporator (Heidolph Laborota 4000) at 40 °C. The dried crude extract was then mixed with water and partitioned with different organic solvent of increasing polarity such as n-hexane, chloroform and ethyl acetate. The aqueous-methanol fraction obtained was concentrated on rotary evaporator. Crude ethanol extract along with its fractions were kept in vials and refrigerated at 4 °C for further analysis.

Determination of Total Phenolic Content

Total phenolic content of the test samples was resolved using Folin-Ciocalteu method employing Gallic acid as standard [15]. 100 µl of the crude sample and its fraction was taken. After which 900 µl of water was added to each extracts. When mixture was prepared then it was provided with 500 µl of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. Then 20 % Na₂CO₃ solution was prepared from which 1.5 ml was taken and added to the above mixture which increased the volume up to 5 ml. Finally this total volume was warmed for two hours. Systronics 2202UV-Vis Spectrophotometer was used for the absorbance at the wavelength of 765 nm. Total phenols were estimated using Gallic acid equivalents (GAE) as standard.

Determination of Total Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content was evaluated using Quercetin as standard [16]. About 5 ml of each extract was mixed with 1 ml water followed by addition of 10 ml ethyl acetate. The mixture was vigorously shaken for 45 minutes. Afterward 100 µl of extract was taken from the mixture in test tube with the addition of 90 µl of phosphate buffer. Now add 3 ml of FCR (1N) and 4 ml of Na₂CO₃ (pH 7.5) to the test tube. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm after incubation period of 45 minutes.

Antioxidant Activity

The EtOH, n-Hex, CHCl₃, EtOAc and AQ fractions was evaluated for antioxidant activity by using 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging technique [17]. The DPPH solution (0.001 M) was prepared by addition of 0.394 g DPPH in 1000 ml distilled water. Now prepare stock solution (500 ppm) by adding 25 mg of each fraction in 50 ml methanol. Afterward 3ml of 1 M DPPH solution was added to the test samples (100 ppm) in one minute followed by addition of 1 ml acetate buffer (pH 6.5). Now vigorously shake the solution for 30 minutes. In case of control solution, 3 ml DPPH was mixed with 1 ml of acetate buffer solution. The antioxidant activity was calculated from the absorbance reading of test samples and control by using the formula:

$$\text{Antioxidant activity} = \frac{100 - (S - B) \times 100}{C}$$

S = Sample absorbance

B = Blank

C = Standard absorbance

Bacterial and Fungal Strains

The antimicrobial activity of crude extract and fractions was evaluated against four opportunistic antimicrobial activity including *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus sp.*, *Xanthomonas sp.*, *Bacillus sp.*, *Penicillium sp.*, *Aspergillus sp.*, *Paecilomyces sp* and *Trichoderma sp.*, respectively.

Medium for Bacterial and Fungal Culturing

Nutrient broth and nutrient agar was used for the culturing and standardization of bacterial strains. About 1.3 g and 2.8 g of nutrient broth and nutrient agar was dissolved in distilled deionized water and the volume was increased up to 100 ml. In case of fungal isolates, potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium was prepared. About 200 gm of peeled potato was dissolved in water and heated until it become soft. Now filter the solution through Muslin cloth and add 20 g of dextrose followed by technical agar to the filtrate. The volume of solution was increased up to 1 L with the help of distilled water. Sterilized the media at 121 °C for 15 minutes at 1.5 psi so that no microbial spores are left.

Antibacterial Bioassay

The antibacterial activity of crude extract and fractions was determined by using disc diffusion method [18]. Take a small streak from the bacterial culture and inoculate in 25 ml nutrient broth using conical flask and then kept on shaker for overnight. Now take 7-8 ml fresh nutrient broth in test tube and decant 100 µl of bacterial inoculum through micropipette. Adjust the turbidity of bacterial culture according to MC Farland standard. Afterward spread

50 µl of bacterial culture on the nutrient agar medium plates. Take Whatmann filter paper discs (6.0 mm diameter) on the four corners of plates and apply the extracts along with pure DMSO as negative and Ciprofloxacin as positive control. Incubate all the plates at 37 °C for 24 hours and measure the zone of inhibition in mm and expressed in percentage by the following formula:

$$\text{Inhibition}(\%) = \frac{\text{Treatment}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Antifungal Bioassay

The *in-vitro* antifungal activity was evaluated by standard well diffusion assay [19]. About 20 ml of PDA medium was poured in sterilize autoclave plates. Now puncture 6 mm well with the help of cork borer in PDA media plates. Apply the desire concentration of each fractions along with positive (Acrobat) and negative control (DMSO) to the wells followed by inoculation of fungal culture. Incubate the plates and observed growth inhibition of fungal isolates after day 7th. Now calculate percent zone of inhibition by the given formula:

$$\text{Inhibition}(\%) = \frac{\text{Control} - \text{Treatment}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Standard procedure was adopted for finding the MIC values of EtOH, *n*-Hex, EtOAc, CHCl₃ and AQ fraction [20]. The crude ethanol extract and various fractions was twofold diluted in DMSO to obtained different concentration of 80, 40, 20, 10, 5, 2.5, 1.25 and 0.625 mg ml⁻¹. Bacterial and fungal cultures were spotted on the plates and each concentration of extract was applied. The bacterial and fungal culture plates were incubated at 37 °C and 27 °C to observe the visible growth of the microorganisms.

Statistical Analysis

The data was recorded in triplicates and analyzed by completely randomized design (CRD) using Statistix 8.1. Analyses of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the significance at 0.05 probability level followed by least significance difference (LSD) to separate similar mean values.

Results

Phytochemical Constituents and Antioxidant Activity

Results depicted in Table 1 divulged that EtOH extract of *T. arjuna* has highest total phenolics (112.60 mg GAE 100 g⁻¹) and flavonoids content (75.0 mg QE 100 g⁻¹) whereas lowest values of 78.9 mg GAE 100 g⁻¹ and 46.3 78.9 mg QE 100 g⁻¹ was examined in CHCl₃ fraction. Notable antioxidant activity was observed in EtOAc (81.20%) as compared to CHCl₃ (76.50%), EtOH (73.60%), AQ (65.50%) and *n*-Hex (55.0%) fractions respectively.

In-vitro Antibacterial Activity

The *in-vitro* antibacterial activity of EtOH, *n*-Hex, EtOAc, CHCl₃ and AQ fractions are presented in Table 2. Results divulge that AQ (75.86%) and EtOH (60.71%) fractions have promising inhibitory zone against *E. coli* with MIC (Table 3) values of 10.0 and 20.0 mg ml⁻¹. However the test bacterial strains were completely resistible to *n*-Hex, EtOAc and CHCl₃ fractions. Likewise maximum inhibitory zone against *Staphylococcus* sp was found for EtOAc as compared to EtOH (63.33%) and CHCl₃ (56.66%) with MIC values of 5.0, 10.0 and 20 mg ml⁻¹ whereas no such potential was examined for *n*-Hex and AQ fractions. Highest activity against *Bacillus* sp was observed for EtOH extract (72.41%) followed by AQ (68.96%), *n*-Hex (53.44%), EtOAc (53.33%) with MIC values of 2.5, 5.0 and 20.0 mg ml⁻¹ whereas CHCl₃ failed to show diameter zone. Against *Xanthomonas* sp., notable inhibitory zone was recorded for AQ (66.66%) and EtOH (57.4%), fractions with MIC values of 20.0 and 40.0 mg ml⁻¹ while no activity was observed for *n*-Hex, CHCl₃ and EtOAc. The MIC value against the bacterial strains ranges from 2.5-40.0 mg ml⁻¹. The lower the MIC value of the extracts higher will be its potential.

In-vitro Antifungal Activity

The promising antifungal activity among the extracts against *Penicillium* sp was examined for AQ (60%) and EtOH (45%) extracts with MIC value of 40.0 and 80.0 mg ml⁻¹. However the fungal species were strongly resistible to *n*-Hex, EtOAc and CHCl₃ fraction. Maximum activity against *Aspergillus* sp was recorded for EtOH (58.33%), CHCl₃ (50%) and EtOAc (44.44%) and AQ (41.66%) fractions with MIC value of 10.0, 20.0 and 40.0 mg ml⁻¹ whereas *n*-Hex fraction was not active against the test fungal isolate. Likewise appreciable fungicidal potential was recorded for AQ fraction against *Paecilomyces* sp (56.81%) with MIC value of 80 mg ml⁻¹ however EtOH, *n*-Hex, EtOAc and CHCl₃ fractions were inactive and don't show inhibitory diameter. Against *Trichoderma* sp notable activity was observed for AQ (63.15%) with MIC value of 10.0 mg ml⁻¹ followed by EtOAc (56.81%), EtOH (52.63%) and CHCl₃ (47.36%) with MIC values of 20.0, 40.0 and 80.0 mg ml⁻¹ respectively. From the present findings it was observed that all the test extracts shows some degree of fungicidal potential except *n*-hexane fraction. The MIC

value against fungal species ranges from 10.0 to 80.0 mg ml⁻¹ which are higher than the antibacterial value therefore representing that fungal strains were more resistible to the extracts as compared to bacterial stains.

Table 1: Phytochemical constituents and antioxidant activity of *T. arjuna*

Extracts	Total Phenolic Content (mg GAE 100 g ⁻¹)	Total Flavonoid Content (mg QE 100 g ⁻¹)	Antioxidant activity (%)
EtOH	112.6	75.0	73.6
<i>n</i> -Hex	101.2	67.3	55.0
EtOAc	113.5	65.8	81.2
CHCl ₃	78.9	46.2	76.5
AQ	108.4	69.1	65.5

GAE = Gallic acid equivalent; QE = Quercetin equivalent

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of crude extract and fractions of *T. arjuna*

Bacterial Strains	Ciprofloxacin (mm)	EtOH	<i>n</i> -Hex	EtOAc	CHCl ₃	AQ
<i>E. coli</i>	28.0	60.71	ND	ND	ND	71.42
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	30.0	63.33	ND	66.66	56.66	ND
<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	29.0	72.41	53.44	53.33	ND	68.96
<i>Xanthomonas sp.</i>	27.0	57.4	ND	ND	ND	66.66

ND = not detected. Each value are mean of three replications (n=R) and highly significant at P<0.05

Table 3: MIC values (mg ml⁻¹) of *T. arjuna* against bacterial strains

Microorganisms	EtOH	<i>n</i> -Hex	EtOAc	CHCl ₃	AQ
<i>E. coli</i>	20	ND	ND	ND	10
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	5	ND	10	20	ND
<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	2.5	20	5	ND	5
<i>Xanthomonas sp.</i>	40	ND	ND	ND	10

ND = not detected

Table 4: Antifungal activity crude extract and fractions of *T. arjuna*

Microorganisms	Acrobat	EtOH	<i>n</i> -Hex	EtOAc	CHCl ₃	AQ
<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	100	45	ND	ND	ND	60
<i>Aspergillus sp.</i>	100	58.33	ND	44.44	50	41.66
<i>Paecilomyces sp.</i>	100	ND	ND	ND	ND	56.81
<i>Trichoderma sp.</i>	100	52.63	ND	56.81	47.36	63.15

ND = not detected. Each value are mean of three replications (n=R) and highly significant at P<0.05

Table 5: MIC values (mg ml⁻¹) for *T. arjuna* against fungal strains

Microorganisms	EtOH	<i>n</i> -Hex	EtOAc	CHCl ₃	AQ
<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	80	ND	ND	ND	40
<i>Aspergillus sp.</i>	10	ND	20	40	20
<i>Paecilomyces sp.</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	80
<i>Trichoderma sp.</i>	20	ND	40	80	10

ND = not detected

Discussion

The various classes of secondary metabolites are present in each part of the plant in the form of phenols and flavonoids [21]. Flavonoids are used for the treatment of cancer, allergies, microbial infection and inflammation. They can modify body's reactions against allergies and viruses and are known as nature biological response modifier [22]. Phenolic compounds exhibit paramount nutrition value by providing flavor, color, aroma and taste. In plants it prevents molecular impairment and damages caused by insects, herbivores and microorganisms [23]. Phenolic moiety displays multifunctional role in the form of reducing agent, antioxidant and metal chelators [24].

The present study was conducted to screen the crude ethanol extract and various fractions of *T. arjuna* for the confirmation of secondary metabolites, antioxidant potential and antimicrobial activities. Therefore reliable pharmacological tests and bioassay techniques are exploited to observe the efficacy of plant extracts [25]. Results depicted in Table 1 shows that total phenolic and flavonoid content of *T. arjuana* ranges from 78.9-112.6 GAE 100g^{-1} and 46.2 to 75.0 mg QE per 100g^{-1} which are in conformity with findings of Kathirvel and Sujatha, 2012 [26]. A lot of phytochemicals can acts as antioxidant by scavenging free radicals that have drastic effects on the body [27-28]. Nowadays antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of extracts have formed the base of modern medication system [29]. Free radical are strong candidates of causing drastic disease such as cardiovascular disorder, stroke, cancer, hypoglycemic, diabetes and inflammation [30]. Among all the test extracts promising antioxidant potential was observed for ethyl acetate fraction having a value of 81.3%. Higher antioxidant values of 94.72% and 91.48% was also reported for methanol and ethanol extract of *T. arjuna* using DPPH assay [31]. Likewise promising antioxidant activity was observed in methanol and aqueous fraction of *T. chebula* which justifies our findings [32]. From the present results it was predicted that antioxidant activities of the extracts might be due to the presence of phenols and flavonoids content.

A variety of toxic compounds produced by plants can act as drugs against harmful microbial isolates as well as unwanted cells [33]. In the recent year antimicrobial activities have been screened because most of the infectious agents were resistant to antibiotics and causes therapeutic problems. Antibacterial and antifungal compounds obtained from plant sources are highly effective in small quantities [34] and are more active than their synthetic counterparts even if similar techniques of their evaluation are used [35]. Quinine and berberine are good examples of antibiotics obtained from plants and are highly effective [36]. Similarly reserpine, taxol and emetine are other examples of phytopharmaceutical agents. Sources of these natural products are *Rauvolfia*, *Taxus* and *Cephaelis* species respectively [35]. The Pharmacological and biological activities such as anti-oxidative, anti-allergic, antibiotic, hypoglycemic and anti-carcinogenic was due to the presence of secondary metabolites in plants [37-39]. The bactericidal activity (Table 2) shows that ethanol fraction have significant inhibitory zone of 72.41% against *Bacillus* sp which are in line with results of Kannan *et al.*, 2009 who observed maximum zone of inhibition of the same extract against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* [40]. The MIC values (Table 3) of extracts against bacterial strains ranges from 2.5 to 40.0mg ml^{-1} . Aneja and Joshi, 2009 reported 12.5 mg ml^{-1} and 25 mg ml^{-1} of MIC values of acetone, methanol, ethanol, cold aqueous and hot aqueous against *S. aureus* and *S. mutans* [41]. The results of the present study were similar to Akhter *et al.*, 2012 who investigated that methanol, ethanol and aqueous fractions have significant bactericidal activity against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* [31]. Our results also finds supportive evidence from the study of Sharma *et al.*, 2011 who investigated that ethyl acetate and ether fraction have notable zone of inhibition against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albican* [42]. Likewise, Naqvi *et al.*, 2010 reported that aqueous, ethyl acetate and ethanol fraction have significant activity against *Candida albican* and *Aspergillus niger* [43]. Devi *et al.*, 2014 observed that petroleum ether, chloroform and aqueous fraction have broad spectrum activity against *Aspergillus Niger*, *Mucor species* and *Rhizopus species* with MIC values of 50mg ml^{-1} and 25mg ml^{-1} respectively [44]. Debnath *et al.*, 2013 determined strong antibacterial and antifungal activity of aqueous and methanol extracts with MIC value ranged from 0.16 to 2.56mg ml^{-1} and 0.16 to 0.64 [45]. Mandloi *et al.*, 2013 investigated that ethanolic extract of *T. Arjuna* have significant fungicidal properties against *Curvularia lunata* (50%), *Aspergillus niger* (47%), *Trichophyton tonsurans* (42%) and *Alternaria alternata* (20.33%) [46]. Jahan *et al.*, (2013) analyzed inhibitory diameter of ethanol extract against *Candida albican* and *Aspergillus niger* [47]. The results of our findings are confirmed from the studied conducted by Nema *et al.*, (2012) who observed that hydro-alcoholic extract of the said plant have strong activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Trichoderma viride* and *Fusariumoxy sporum* [48].

Conclusion

It was concluded that crude ethanol extract and its frascion possess appreciable amount of total phenols and flavonoids moiety. Likewise the plant extracts also exhibit promising antioxidant activity along with notable antimicrobial activity against opportunistic bacterial and fungal isolates indicating that the active ingredients are broad spectrum. It was observed from the experimental results that the presence of phenols and flavonoid content in the said plant might be the possible reasons for its antioxidant and antimicrobial activity. Therefore further research work is required to isolate and characterize such bioactive compounds that are responsible for different biological and pharmacological activities by using advance chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques.

References

1. Roopashree, T.S., Dang, R., Rani, R.H.S., & Narendra, C. (2008). Antibacterial activity of antipsoriatic herbs: *Cassia tora*, *Momordica charantia* and *Calendula officinalis*. *International Journal of Applied Research in Natural Products*, 1(3), 20-28.
2. Kavitha, D., & Padma, P.R. (2011). A study of the antimicrobial effect of *Albizia amara* leaf extracts. *Advances in Plant Science*, 24(1): 49-52.
3. Shivaii, R., Naveet, S., & Jain, A.K. (2011). Antimicrobial activity of medicinal plants against vaginal pathogens. *Advances in Plant Science*, 24(1): 53-55.
4. Parabia, F.M., Kathari, I.L., & Parabia, M.H. (2008). Antibacterial activity of solvent fractions of crude water decoction of apical twigs of latex of *Calotropis procera* (Ait.) R. Br. *Natural Product Radiance*, 7(1): 30-34.
5. Ramkumar, K.M., Rajaguru, P., & Ananthan, R. (2007). Antimicrobial properties and phytochemical constituents of an antidiabetic plant *Gymnema montanum*. *Advances in Biological Research*, 1: 67-71.
6. Warriar, P.K., Nambiar, V.P.K., & Ramankutty, C. (1994). *Indian Medicinal Plants. A Compendium of 500 species*, Orient Longman, Madras, India
7. Nadkarni, A.K. (1976). *Indian Materia Medica*. 1st Edn., Popular Prakash, Mumbai, India.
8. Bhat, D.M., Swami, V.S., & Rabindranath, N.H. (2003). *Nursery manual for forest tree species*. University Press (Ind.) Private Limited, 274-275.
9. Udupa, K.N. (1986). Scope of use of *Terminalia arjuna* in ischaemic heart disease. *Annals of the National Academy of medical sciences*, 1, 54.
10. Jain, S., Yadav, P.P., Gill, V., Vasudeva, N., & Singla, N. (2009) *Terminalia arjuna* a sacred medicinal plant; phytochemical and pharmacological profile. *Phytochemistry Reviews*, 8(2): 491-502.
11. Tripathi, V.K., & Singh, B. (1996). *Terminalia arjuna*- its present status (A Review). *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 12(1): 1-16.
12. Cowan, M.M. (1999). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 12(4): 564-82.
13. Sher, A. (2009). Antimicrobial activity of natural products from medicinal plants. *Gomal Journal of Medical Sciences*, 7(1): 72-78.
14. Das, K., Tiwari, R.K.S., & Shrivastava, D.K. (2010). Techniques for evaluation of medicinal plant products as antimicrobial agent: current methods and future trends. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 4(2): 104-111.
15. Yu, L., Haley, S., Perret, J., Harris, M., Wilson, J., & Qian, M. (2002). Free radical scavenging properties of wheat extracts. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 50: 1619-1624.
16. Sharma, R.J., Chaphalkar, S.R., & Adsool, A.D. (2010). Evaluating antioxidant potential, cytotoxicity and intestinal absorption of flavonoids extracted from medicinal plant. *International Journal of Biotechnology Applications*, 2(1): 1-5.
17. Akond, A.S.G.M., Khandaker, L., Birthhold, J., Gates, L., Peters, K., Delong, H., & Hossain, K. (2011). Anthocyanin, total phenol and antioxidant activity of common bean. *American Journal of Food Technology*, 6: 385-394.
18. Tassou, C., Koutsoumanis, K., & Nychas, J.G.J.E. (2000). Inhibition of *Salmonella enteritidis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in nutrient broth by mint essential oil. *Food Research International*, 33: 273-280.
19. Rusman, Y. (2006). Isolation of new secondary metabolites from sponges associated and plant derived endophytic fungi. PhD thesis. Heinrich Heine University Dusseldorf.
20. Nostro, A., Germano, M.P., Angelo, V.D., & Cannatelli, M.A. (2000). Extraction methods and bio autography for evaluation of medicinal plant antimicrobial activity. *Letters Applied Microbiology*, 30: 379-384.
21. Mathew, S., & Abraham, T.E. (2006). Studies on the antioxidant activities of cinnamon (*Cinnamomum verum*) bark extracts, through various in vitro models. *Food Chemistry*, 94: 520-528.
22. Aiyelaagbe, O.O., & Osamudiamen, P.M. (2009). Phytochemical screening for active compounds in *Mangifera indica*. *Plant Sciences Research*, 2(1): 11-13.
23. Vaya, J., Belinky, P.A., & Aviram, M. (1997). Antioxidant constituents from Licorice roots: isolation, structure elucidation and anti-oxidative capacity toward LDL oxidation. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 23(2): 302-313.

24. Shahidi, F., & Naczki, M. (2003). Phenolics in food and nutraceuticals, London, UK, CRC Press, 403-422.
25. Hussain, A., Zia, M., & Mirza, B. (2007). Cytotoxic and antitumor potential of *Fagonia cretica* L. *Turkish Journal of Biology*, 4(31): 19-24.
26. Kathirvel, A., & Sujatha, V. (2012). In vitro assessment of antioxidant and antibacterial properties of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. Leaves. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 788-795.
27. Hausladen, A., & Stamler, J.S. (1999). Nitrosative stress. *Methods in Enzymology*, 300: 389-395.
28. Lee, Y.M., Kim, H., Hong, E.K., Kang, B.H., & Kim, S.J. (2000). Water extract of 1:1 mixture of Phellodendron cortex and Aralia cortex has inhibitory effects on oxidative stress in kidney of diabetic rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 73: 429-436.
29. Abiy, Y., Solmon, D., Jacob, D.M., Christine, C.B., Matthias, H., & Martin, G.P. (2005). Antimicrobial flavonoids from the stem bark of *Erythrina burtii*. *Fitoterapia*, 96: 496-499.
30. Scalbert, A., Manach, C., Remesy, C., & Morand, C. (2005). Dietary polyphenols and the prevention of diseases. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 45: 287-306.
31. Akhter, S., Hossain, M.I., Haque, M.A., Shahriar, M., & Bhuiyan, M.A. (2012). Phytochemical screening, antibacterial, antioxidant and cytotoxic activity of the bark extract of *Terminalia Arjuna*. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 86(4): 543-552.
32. Sarwar, S., Malik, A.H., Rahman, M.A., Rahman, M.Z., & Rana, M.S. (2013). Antioxidant, cytotoxic and analgesic activities of the methanolic fruit extract of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. *International Current Pharmaceutical Journal*, 3(1): 219-222.
33. Mans, D.R., da Rocha, A.B., & Schwartzmann, G. (2000). Anti-cancer drug discovery and development in Brazil: targeted plant collection as a rational strategy to acquire candidate anti-cancer compounds. *Oncologist*, 5: 185-198.
34. Gibbons, S. (2005). An introduction to planar chromatography In: Natural product isolation edited by Sarker, S.D., Latif, Z., Gray, A.I. Humana press, p. 77-116.
35. Iwu, M.W., Duncan, A.R., & Okunji, C.O. (1999). New antimicrobials of plant origin In: Perspectives on new crops and new uses, edited by Janick, J., ASHS Press, Alexandria, VA, 1999, p. 457-462.
36. Maridass, M., & De Britto, A.J. (2008). Origins of plant derived medicines. *Ethnobotanical Leaflets* 12: 373-387.
37. Katalinic, V., Milo, M., Kulisic, T., & Jukic, M. (2004). Screening of 70 medicinal plant extracts for antioxidant capacity and total phenols. *Food Chemistry*, 94: 550-557.
38. Mulabagal, V., & Tsay, H. (2004). Plant Cell Cultures - an alternative and efficient source for the production of biologically important secondary metabolites. *International Journal of Applied Science Engineering*, 2: 29-48.
39. Borneo, R., Leon, E.A., Aguirre, A., Ribotta, P., & Cantero, J.J. (2008). Antioxidant capacity of medicinal plants from the Province of Cordoba (Argentina) and their in vitro testing in model food system. *Food Chemistry*, 112: 664-670.
40. Kannan, P., Ramadevi, S.R., & Hopper, W. (2009). Antibacterial activity of *Terminalia chebula* fruit extract. *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, 3: 180-184.
41. Aneja, K.R., & Joshi, R. (2009). Evaluation of antimicrobial properties of fruit extracts of *Terminalia chebula* against dental caries pathogens. *Jundishapur Journal of Microbiology*, 2(3): 105-111.
42. Sharma, A., Meena, S., & Barman, N. (2011). Efficacy of ethyl acetate and ether extract of *Terminalia chebula* Retz against some human pathogenic strains. *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, 3(2): 724-727.
43. Naqvi, S.H.R., Asif, M., Rehman, A., & Ahmad, M. (2010). Evaluation of antimicrobial properties of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. *Pakistan Journal of Pharmacology*, 27(1): 29-35.
44. Devi, R.S., Narayan, S., Vani, G., & C.S.S. Devi (2007). Gastro protective effect of *Terminalia arjuna* bark on diclofenac sodium induced gastric ulcer. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*, 167: 71-83.
45. Debnath, S., Dey, D., Hazra, S., Ghosh, S., Ray, R., & Hazra, B. (2013). Antibacterial and antifungal activity of *Terminalia arjuna* Wight and Arn. bark against multi-drug resistant clinical isolates. *Journal of Coastal Life Medicine*, 1 (4): 315-321.
46. Mandloi, S., Srinivasa, R., Mishra, R., & Verma, R. (2013). Antifungal activity of alcohol leaf extracts of *Terminalia Catappa* and *Terminalia Arjuna* on some pathogenic and allergenic fungi. *Advances in Life Sciences and Technology*, 8: 25-28.

47. Jahan, N., Ahmad, M., Mehjabeen., Sherwani, S.K.,& Naqvi, G.R. (2013). Antimicrobial potential against microbes found in clinical samples and toxicity studies on selected medicinal plants. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy*, 4(4): 109-112.
48. Nema, R., Jain, P., Khare, S., Pradhan, A., Gupta, A.,& Singh, D. (2012). Antibacterial and antifungal activity of *Terminalia Arjuna* leaves extract with special reference to flavanoids. *Basic Research Journal of Medicine and Clinical Science*, 1(5): 63-65.

